

CANINE BRUCELLOSIS

DESCRIPTION AND SIGNIFICANCE

Canine-specific brucellosis due to *Brucella canis* is an infectious and contagious disease, which mainly results in epizootic and enzootic abortions as well as infertility in both males and females. Recently several cases of dogs with spondylodiscitis or other non-reproductive symptoms have been identified. *Brucella* spp. is the causative agent of brucellosis, which is transmissible to humans and has a worldwide distribution.

Brucella spp. are class 3 bacteria and, with the exception of *B. ovis*, are subject to MOT (highly pathogenic microorganisms and toxins) regulations. The *Brucella* genus includes twelve species classified according to their pathogenicity and their preferred hosts (terrestrial and marine mammals or amphibians). Bacteria of the genus *Brucella* present so-called smooth or rough phenotypes depending on the type of polysaccharide O: *B. canis* and *B. ovis* present the rough type, while other species have a smooth form of polysaccharide (except *B. inopinata*). These groups have different antigenic characteristics, which means that the serological tests applied to rough species are different from those used for smooth ones. The species presenting a smooth polysaccharide on their surface show the highest virulence potential. *B. canis* was discovered in 1966 - 1967 in the USA during a study of abortion in beagles, the organism was isolated from aborted tissue and vaginal discharge. Canids (domestic and wild) are the natural reservoirs of *B. canis*. It should be noted that in areas where animal brucellosis is endemic, canine infections with *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus*, and *B. suis* (with the potential for transmission to humans) may occur when dogs come in contact with infected livestock (spill-over), or consume produce from infected animals.

SOURCES OF INFECTION

Infected animals excrete contaminated discharges into the environment (contents of the pregnant uterus, vaginal secretions, urine, milk, semen, suppuration products). Contamination occurs through the oronasal, conjunctival and genital mucosa. Sexual transmission (mating, licking after abortion) is also a cause of contamination. Indirect contamination, via relaxation areas, housing and shared equipment (food and water bowls, veterinary equipment, etc.) must be considered in places where dogs are in larger numbers (breeding, shelters, gatherings ...). Aerosol transmission is possible and would play a role in the dissemination of the disease within the group. The survival of *Brucella* spp. in the environment is favoured in humid conditions and at low temperatures ($\leq 4^{\circ}\text{C}$). When conditions are optimal, *Brucella* spp. can survive for more than two months in water at 20°C , two to four months in soil and on fresh grass in a moist environment and/or in the presence of organic waste.

The species affected by *B. canis* are canids, with frequent transmission by direct contact with infected biological fluids, by oral or respiratory route. Vulvar discharges may remain contaminated for several weeks. Excretion in semen and urine is frequently observed within 4-8 weeks of infection, after which may remain intermittent for several months or even years. In humans, contamination is possible for persons in close contact with dogs (repeated contact, cleaning, whelping, surgery on infected animals, contact with secretions, urine and faeces of infected dogs) or by laboratory exposure.

Prevention is based on general hygiene measures (wearing gloves, hand hygiene, cleaning litter boxes) and even wearing a surgical mask in high-risk situations. In case of suspicion or at risk, it is recommended to implement biosecurity measures in kennels. For example, small groups of dogs should be kept when new dogs are introduced; six-week quarantine with serological testing at the beginning and end of quarantine; testing of animals from endemic areas; testing of males used for breeding.

A RARE ZONOSIS

Human infections are rare, but probably underestimated because of the possibility of asymptomatic cases and the lack of a validated indirect diagnostic technique. The first observations of human infection with *B. canis* isolated from blood cultures date from the 1970s. In almost all cases, contact with a domestic dog is identified, and in some cases, contact with a dog infected with *B. canis* is well documented, especially during miscarriage. Children can get infected as well. The clinical manifestations and severity of *B. canis* infections do not appear to differ from those observed with infections with other *Brucella* species. When symptomatic, the infection may take different clinical forms, including several nonspecific symptoms such as intermittent fever, chills, loss of appetite, weight loss, headache, backache, or joint pain...

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CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION

Since November 2021, *B. canis* infections have been confirmed in five commercial kennels, located in five different French departments, following reports of late miscarriage in bitches of various breeds, including animals imported from Russia or Belarus via online purchases. Two other dogs with spondylodiscitis owned by individuals were also confirmed with *B. canis* infection by the National Reference Laboratory for Brucellosis (ANSES) during this period. This disease remains endemic in dogs in many parts of the world, with a predominance in Central and South America, Asia, and the southern United States. Over the past 20 years, published studies in these endemic areas have reported moderate to high seroprevalence, ranging from approximately 6% to 35%. In Europe, various cases have been described over the past decade in Austria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Sweden, Switzerland, and the United Kingdom. The emergence of canine brucellosis seems to be accelerated in Western Europe since 2020. In Italy, *B. canis* infection was first reported in 2020 in a large kennel. Similarly, in the United Kingdom, cases have increased since July 2020 in association with rise of dog imports during the COVID-19 outbreak.

When to suspect canine brucellosis?

In the bitch, the easiest sign to recognize is a **late abortion** that occurs between day 45 of gestation and term. However, abortion may occur earlier and go unnoticed: the bitch is apparently infertile. Smaller litters (embryonic resorption) or stillborn puppies are also observed. Some puppies survive and remain infected and therefore potential reservoirs. In males, *B. canis* infection frequently causes **chronic epididymitis**, which is almost asymptomatic, but which can lead to an alteration of the spermogram within a few weeks. More rarely, orchitis and/or prostatitis can be observed. **The infection can remain asymptomatic**, even if the animal excretes the bacteria in the semen and urine. Other symptoms suggestive of brucellosis should be taken into account: **locomotor disorders** (lameness, muscle weakness, vertebral osteitis, discospondylitis) or non-specific symptoms (lethargy, weight loss, lymphadenopathy, uveitis).

There are **two main types of laboratory diagnostic approaches** to detect and confirm canine brucellosis:

1 - Serological tests or indirect diagnosis allow the detection of antibodies directed against rough *Brucella* (*B. canis* or *B. ovis*) from serum (blood sample in dry tube). These tests are useful for screening and monitoring of kennels. They are the least expensive tests and can be performed on all animals in case of suspicion and then repeated every four to six weeks to monitor the infection levels. The main limitations are related to **the possibility of false positive results or non-detection of seronegative infected dogs** (too close to beginning of infection, considering the delay of seroconversion; or on the contrary, old infection with a decreasing antibody titer);

2 - Direct diagnosis aims to identify the bacteria (search and isolation) from blood samples (preferably citrated tubes), tissues or biological fluids. The bacterial genome can be detected from a sample by molecular amplification techniques (PCR targeting the DNA of the *Brucella* genus).

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Identification of the *B. canis* species can be done by bacteriology, molecular amplification (PCR) or mass spectrometry (MALDI-TOF). These approaches allow confirmation of infection and (geno)typing of strains. The main limitation is the lack of sensitivity of these approaches: **a negative result does not mean that the animal is uninfected**, as the bacteria may be present in small quantities (below the PCR detection limit) or have low viability. Misidentification by MALDI-TOF is possible (confusion with the genus *Ochrobactrum*). **Repeated sampling is necessary to increase the chances of detecting the bacteria.**

Situation	Indirect diagnostics	Direct diagnostics	Further actions
Symptoms similar to brucellosis	Yes (<i>B. canis</i> tests + EAT/ELISA if there is also risk of infection with smooth <i>Brucella</i> spp.)	Yes (according to lesions / symptoms)	If sero-negative – repeat blood sampling after 4 to 6 weeks + if necessary, repeat sampling for bacterial isolation
Asymptomatic	Yes (rapid tests)	No	If sero-positive – collect samples for direct diagnostic (whole blood, genital swabs, urine, semen)

What to do if the suspicion is confirmed?

In a kennel, it is essential to immediately isolate all seropositive animals and implement appropriate biosecurity and disinfection measures. In a case of positive serological results, all animals must be tested. Serological tests should be repeated at least twice at 4-6 weeks intervals. Mating should be stopped during the sanitation period as well as animal exchanges. Additional samples should be taken to confirm the infection, and sent to the competent authorities. **Positive results (serological tests, cultures and DNA detection by PCR) should be reported by the qualified veterinary services.**

Two control options are to be considered for infected dogs:

1. Euthanasia of infected dogs. This measure ensures the protection of other animals and people in contact with the infected animal;
2. Surgical sterilization and long term antibiotic treatment (dual therapy, 4 to 8 weeks). It is essential to note that currently, antibiotics cannot cure all cases. The positive animal has to be isolated and removed from the kennel to avoid further contamination of other dogs, and will have to be followed for life (risk of relapse). Antibiotic treatment is aggressive and can be accompanied by undesirable effects as well (liver and kidney toxicity).

Finally, the absence of clinical symptoms after treatment does not guarantee the absence of the bacteria.

FOR FURTHER READING:

- ANSES (2022). [La brucellose canine](#)

- APHA (2021). [Canine Brucellosis: Summary Information Sheet \(defra.gov.uk\)](#)

-Avis du Haut conseil de la santé publique (18 mars 2022). [Conduite à tenir vis-à-vis de personnes exposées à des animaux atteints de Brucellose canine \(hcsp.fr\)](#)

-Brucella spp. <http://www.anses.fr/fr/system/files/BIORISK2013sa0188.pdf>

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